

The myotonic dystrophy type 1 drug development pipeline: 2026 Edition

KEYNOTE

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Over the past few years, therapeutic development for myotonic dystrophy type 1 has accelerated markedly, with ongoing clinical trials nearly doubling and several candidates advancing to late-stage evaluation. Approaches have diversified, including small molecules, antibody–oligonucleotide conjugates, enhanced-delivery antisense platforms, gene therapy and miRNA-targeting strategies. Several nucleic-acid-based therapies demonstrate robust target engagement and clinically meaningful signals, positioning this modality as highly promising for disease modification. Parallel preclinical research has expanded the range of mechanisms under investigation, while structured exercise and rehabilitation continue to emerge as complementary nonpharmacological interventions. Together, these developments illustrate a therapeutic landscape entering an unprecedented phase of maturity, with multiple avenues progressing simultaneously toward potential clinical translation.

Keywords: myotonic dystrophy; CTG repeat expansion; antisense oligonucleotides; drug repurposing; nucleic acid therapeutics; gene therapy; clinical trials

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Introduction

Myotonic dystrophy type 1 (DM1, OMIM 160900) is an autosomal dominant genetic disorder and constitutes the most prevalent form of muscular dystrophy in the adult population. The disease is characterized by progressive degeneration of both skeletal and smooth muscle tissues, together with involvement of the central nervous system (CNS). Although classified as a neuromuscular disorder, DM1 displays a multisystemic clinical profile. Consequently, while the principal manifestations include progressive muscle weakness, myotonia and a gradual decline in cognitive function, the disorder also affects other organs and systems such as the heart, the gastrointestinal tract or the eyes.^(p1) Both quality of life and life expectancy are significantly reduced in affected individuals, and the disease may become life-threatening when it compromises cardiac or respiratory muscles.^(p2) The pooled estimate for the prevalence of DM1 is stated as 1 case per 10 000 individuals.^(p3) However, a different study based on genetic screening data suggests that DM1 may be significantly more prevalent, up to five times higher, affecting approximately 4.8 in every 10 000 individuals.^(p4) This finding indicates widespread underdiagnosis and positions DM1 among the most common rare diseases.

DM1 is caused by the expansion of a CTG trinucleotide repeat located in the 3' untranslated region (3'UTR) of the *DMPK* gene on chromosome 19q13.3.^(p5) In unaffected individuals, the repeat length is typically ≤ 35 units, whereas pathogenic alleles generally contain ≥ 50 repeats. Alleles with an intermediate size (35–49 repeats) are usually non-penetrant; however, this microsatellite region is unstable and prone to further expansion upon transmission to offspring, leading to genetic anticipation.^(p6) These expansions generate abnormal *DMPK* transcripts with long CUG repeat tracts [(CUG)*exp*] that adopt secondary structures, forming discrete nuclear RNA foci and leading to a toxic RNA gain-of-function effect.^(p7) The more accepted mechanism involves the sequestration of RNA-binding proteins of the muscleblind-like splicing regulators (MBNL) family, trapped by the (CUG)*exp*. MBNL proteins are essential regulators of alternative splicing, and their functional depletion results in widespread spliceopathy in DM1.^(p8) Notably, the Myotonic Dystrophy Splice Index (SI), a composite RNA splicing measure based on 22 MBNL-dependent, disease-specific events, has recently been validated as a reliable biomarker of DM1 muscle weakness. The SI associates RNA mis-splicing with strength and mobility and provides prognostic insight into future functional outcomes, supporting its application in therapeutic target engagement.^(p9) The MBNL protein family comprises three paralogs, among which MBNL1 and MBNL2, predominantly active in skeletal muscle and the CNS, respectively, colocalize with RNA foci in affected cells.^{(p10),(p11)}

Simultaneously, the protein expression level of CUGBP Elav-like family member 1 (CUGBP1 or CELF1) is upregulated in DM1 skeletal muscle and cardiac tissue samples.^{(p12),(p13)} CELF1 also plays a crucial role in the regulation of alternative splicing but, in contrast to MBNL proteins, does not colocalize with RNA foci.^{(p14),(p15),(p16)} CELF1 upregulation is driven by stress-

responsive signaling pathways, primarily through protein kinase C-mediated hyperphosphorylation, which increases protein stability by prolonging its half-life.^(p17) Another mechanism that contributes to CELF1 upregulation is the activation of glycogen synthase kinase 3 beta (GSK3 β). In DM1, pathologically elevated GSK3 β phosphorylates cyclin D3, targeting it for proteasomal degradation. As cyclin D3 is the regulatory subunit required for cyclin-dependent kinase 4 (CDK4) activation, the loss of cyclin D3 impairs CDK4-dependent CELF1 phosphorylation and function. Consequently, CELF1 is no longer phosphorylated by CDK4 at sites that normally promote its turnover, leading to its accumulation in the nucleus.^{(p18),(p19),(p20)} CELF1 and MBNLs perform antagonistic roles in the regulation of alternative splicing. MBNLs promote the inclusion of adult-specific isoforms, whereas CELF1 drives the expression of fetal isoforms. Thus, dysregulation of these factors leads to a reversion toward fetal splicing patterns in DM1 patients.^{(p21),(p22)} This widespread misregulation accounts for a few of the clinical manifestations observed in patients.^{(p23),(p24)} miRNA dysregulation is also increasingly recognized as a contributor to DM1 pathology. Notably, elevated levels of miR-23b and miR-218, natural repressors of MBNL1, have been observed in DM1 samples, further exacerbating MBNL1 depletion and amplifying the splicing defects characteristic of the disease.^(p25) In addition to the primary molecular defects, several additional mechanisms help to explain DM1 pathology. Dysregulation of interconnected signaling pathways, including *Akt-mTOR*, *AMPK*, *PKR*, calcineurin and *TWEAK-Fn14*, contributes to muscle atrophy, metabolic imbalance, impaired regeneration and inflammation-driven fibrosis.^(p26) It has also been reported that loss of the transcription factor MEF2 in DM1 hearts leads to downregulation of miRNAs that normally suppress fibrosis, contributing to fibrotic remodeling.^(p27) In the brains of DM1 patients, loss of cytoplasmic MBNL1 impairs BDNF-TrkB retrograde signaling, leading to neuronal dysfunction and potentially contributing to neurodegeneration.^(p28) However, CNS involvement in DM1 is multifactorial and also includes widespread alternative splicing defects affecting transcripts such as *MAPT* (tau) and *APP*, among others.^{(p29),(p30)} Additionally, dysregulation of *MECP2*-dependent pathways, essential for excitatory glutamatergic synaptic signaling, has been linked to neurodevelopmental defects in DM1.^(p31) Finally, individuals with DM1 frequently report additional, less-characterized manifestations, including gastrointestinal symptoms, which further highlight the multisystemic nature of the disease.^(p32)

Despite extensive scientific efforts and a deep understanding of the disease, DM1 patients still do not have approved drugs available. This review, an updated version of the close follow-up started at the beginning of this decade,^(p33) highlights the most recent advances in therapeutic development for DM1, from the appearance of new preclinical strategies to drugs currently in clinical evaluation. Notably, over the past years, several therapeutic candidates have advanced into late-stage clinical development, including Phase III trials, bringing the prospect of effective disease-modifying treatments for DM1 closer than ever, while

the field has simultaneously broadened to encompass complementary, nonpharmacological strategies aimed at improving functional and cognitive outcomes.

Clinical trial developments

Building on our previous review,^(p33) here we highlight advances from the past 3 years, providing an overview of the 15 molecules currently in clinical development for DM1. Therapeutic candidates are broadly classified into three categories: small molecules, biological therapies and nucleic acid therapies (NATs). Clinical-stage treatments involve a growing range of strategies, aiming to cover from alleviating symptoms up to targeting the underlying disease-linked molecular defects (Table 1; Figure 1).

Small molecules

Small molecules are low-molecular-weight synthetic compounds that interact with biological targets to mimic, enhance or inhibit natural molecules.^(p34) Their usually simple structure confers advantages such as stability, tissue distribution, reproducibility and flexible design for final administration (tablets, inhalers and injectables), but at the same time can limit potency or specificity, commonly displaying off-target effects. Linked to small molecule developments, drug repurposing strategy is widely employed in drug discovery, especially in rare diseases, as it accelerates approval processes by using compounds whose safety has already been established in other diseases, thereby offering a cost-effective and time-efficient pathway to translate treatments into clinical practice.^{(p35),(p36)} Consequently, several repurposed small molecules have been, and a few still are, investigated in DM1 therapy. This includes not only **mexiletine**, **tideglusib** and **metformin**, all three already in Phase III, but also others in earlier clinical evaluation steps like **pitolisant**, **amlodipine**, **erythromycin**, **DT-818** and **lamotrigine**.

Mexiletine

Mexiletine is classified as a class Ib antiarrhythmic agent, blocking voltage-gated sodium channels, including Nav1.5 in cardiac muscle and Nav1.4 in skeletal muscle.^(p37) By reducing Nav1.4-mediated hyperexcitability, one of the key contributors to delayed muscle relaxation, mexiletine stabilizes skeletal muscle membrane excitability and alleviates myotonia.^(p38) In 2018, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) approved mexiletine (marketed as NaMuscla by Lupin Pharmaceutical) for the symptomatic treatment of nondystrophic myotonias^(p39); however, it has not yet been approved for the treatment of DM1. Given its antiarrhythmic properties, concerns have been raised regarding the possibility that mexiletine may induce *de novo* arrhythmias or worsen pre-existing conduction abnormalities in patients with DM1.^(p40) However, long-term clinical studies have generally reported reassuring safety outcomes in the DM1 population.^(p41) Even so, experts advise caution in patients with high-risk cardiac involvement. In these individuals, mexiletine may exacerbate conduction defects or promote ventricular arrhythmias, making comprehensive cardiac evaluation essential prior to treatment initiation.^(p38) Mexiletine was first evaluated in two pivotal randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled crossover trials in 2010, demonstrating that doses of 150 and 200 mg three times daily over 7 weeks were well tolerated and signifi-

cantly reduced handgrip myotonia.^(p42) A subsequent Phase II study (NCT01406873), sponsored by the University of Rochester, extended these findings over 6 months and showed that mexiletine not only improved myotonia but also enhanced muscle strength, functional performance, pain and patient-reported quality of life, further supporting its safety profile.^(p43)

Mexiletine then advanced to Phase III in the MIND study (NCT04700046), a multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial designed to evaluate long-term efficacy and safety in DM1 adult patients over 26 weeks. This study was withdrawn in May 2024 to explore novel alternative study designs and regulatory pathways prior to its planned completion in July 2024. A new Phase III clinical trial, HERCULES (NCT06523400 or MEX-DM-302), is currently ongoing, maintaining the same overall design as the previous study but using a prolonged-release (PR) formulation intended to improve tolerability and patient convenience by avoiding plasma peaks associated with the standard formulation used in the MIND trial. Participants completing HERCULES may join the open-label ATLAS extension study (NCT06549400 or MEX-DM-303), receiving mexiletine PR for 18 months to assess long-term safety and durability of response.

Metformin

Metformin, originally developed as an oral antidiabetic for its ability to suppress hepatic glucose production and enhance insulin sensitivity, has been repurposed for DM1 due to its potential to modulate RNA toxicity and associated splicing defects.^(p44) Metformin accumulates in mitochondria and partially inhibits respiratory chain complex I, leading to an increased AMP/ATP ratio and activation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK). AMPK activation reduces the expression of the RNA-binding protein RBM3, and this downregulation contributes to the correction of a subset of DM1-associated alternative splicing defects, likely through modulation of the splicing machinery downstream of toxic CUG RNA accumulation. Although this mechanism does not involve direct evidence of MBNL protein release from CUG RNA foci, partial restoration of normal splicing has been observed for several disease-relevant transcripts, including insulin receptor (*INSR*) and chloride channel (*CLCN1*).^(p45) However, metformin also exerts effects through AMPK-independent pathways, and its full mechanism of action in DM1 remains incompletely understood.^(p45) Together, these findings position metformin as a modulator of early molecular pathogenic events with downstream improvements in selected disease features, including muscle function and mitochondrial integrity, although its effects are limited to a subset of molecular and clinical endpoints.^(p44)

Early Phase II trials demonstrated that metformin improves mobility in DM1 patients, as assessed by the 6-minute walk test (6MWT), with a favorable safety profile, while effects on myotonia and muscle strength were more modest.^(p46) European clinical trials have contributed to this evidence base, including EudraCT 2013-001732-21 (Phase II) and 2018-000692-32 (Phase III). These studies laid the groundwork for the ongoing Phase III METFORMYO trial (NCT05532813; EudraCT 2023-507660-39-00) at the Hôpitaux de Paris, which aims to comprehensively evaluate metformin's efficacy on muscle function in a larger DM1 cohort. Recruitment is currently underway.

TABLE 1

Drugs currently in clinical trials for DM1.

Therapeutic agent	Type	Biological target	Clinical trial name	Clinical trial code	Phase	Status	Estimated enrollment	Sponsor	Results
Metformin	Small molecule (repurposed)	Mitochondrial complex I (AMPK activation)	Evaluation of the efficacy and safety of metformin in myotonic dystrophy type 1 (METFORMYO)	NCT05532813	III	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	142	Assistance Publique—Hôpitaux de Paris	Review in Ref. (p31)
Mexiletine	Small molecule (repurposed)	Voltage-gated sodium channels (Nav1.4)	Open-label extension study to evaluate long-term safety and efficacy of once daily mexiletine PR in DM1/DM2 (MEX-DM-OLE)	NCT06549400	III	Recruiting (Est. completion 2028)	176	Lupin	6MWT: Mexiletine 17.44 m vs. Placebo 7.25 m
			The efficacy and safety of once daily mexiletine PR in patients with DM1 and DM2	NCT06523400	III	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	176	Lupin	No results provided
AOC 1001 (<i>del-desiran</i>)	NAT (siRNA-Ab conjugate)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	Global study of <i>del-desiran</i> for the treatment of DM1 (HARBOR-OLE)	NCT07008469	III	Recruiting (Est. completion 2030)	230	Avidity Biosciences	No results provided
			Global study of <i>del-desiran</i> for the treatment of DM1 (HARBOR)	NCT06411288	III	Active, not recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	159	Avidity Biosciences	Positive long-term MARINA-OLE data; reversal of disease progression; common AEs: procedural pain, headache (p81)
Tideglusib	Small molecule (repurposed)	GSK3 β	Safety and efficacy of tideglusib in congenital/childhood-onset DM (REACH CDM X)	NCT05004129	II/III	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	76	AMO Pharma Ltd	No results provided
			Expanded access use in congenital myotonic dystrophy DM	NCT07119775	N/A	Active, not recruiting	N/A	AMO Pharma Ltd	No results provided
Erythromycin (MYD-0124)	Small molecule (repurposed)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	Safety and efficacy trial of MYD-0124 for myotonic dystrophy type 1	JRCT2051190069	II	Completed	30	Nakamori Masayuki—Osaka University Hospital	No results provided
PGN-EDODM1	NAT (PMO)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	A clinical study of PGN-EDODM1 in people with DM1 (FREEDOM2-DM1)	NCT06667453	II	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	24	PepGen Inc.	No results provided
			Open-label extension study of PGN-EDODM1 (FREEDOM-OLE)	NCT07220603	II	Not yet recruiting (Est. completion 2029)	48	PepGen Inc.	No results provided
VX-670	NAT (PMO)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	Long-term safety and efficacy of VX-670 in participants with DM1	NCT06926621	II	Enrolling by invitation (Est. completion 2028)	36	Vertex Pharmaceuticals	No results provided

TABLE 1 (CONTINUED)

Therapeutic agent	Type	Biological target	Clinical trial name	Clinical trial code	Phase	Status	Estimated enrollment	Sponsor	Results
			Study of VX-670 in adult participants with DM1 (Galileo)	NCT06185764	I/II	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	36	Vertex Pharmaceuticals	No results provided
Pitolisant	Small molecule (repurposed)	Histamine H3 receptor (antagonist)	Safety and efficacy of pitolisant on daytime sleepiness in DM1	NCT04886518	II	Completed (2024)	30	Harmony Biosciences	No detailed findings
DYNE-101 (z-basivarsen)	NAT (gapmer-Fab conjugate)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	Safety, tolerability, pharmacodynamic, efficacy and pharmacokinetic study of DYNE-101 in participants with myotonic dystrophy type 1 (ACHIEVE)	NCT05481879	I/II	Recruiting (Est. completion 2029)	116	Dyne Therapeutics	No results published
ARO-DM1 (SRP-1003)	NAT (siRNA)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	A Phase I/IIa dose-escalating study to evaluate the safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of ARO-DM1 in subjects with type 1 myotonic dystrophy	NCT06138743	I/II	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	78	Arrowhead/Sarepta	No results provided
SAR446268	NAT (AAV-RNAi)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	A study to investigate the safety, tolerability and efficacy of SAR446268, an adeno-associated viral vector-mediated gene therapy in participants aged 10–50 years of age with noncongenital myotonic dystrophy type 1 (BrAAVe)	NCT06844214	I/II	Recruiting (Est. completion 2030)	32	Sanofi	No results provided
ATX-01	NAT (antimiRNA-oleic acid conjugate)	microRNA-23b	Study of ATX-01 in participants with DM1 (ArthemIR)	NCT06300307	I/II	Recruiting (Est. completion 2026)	56	ARTHEX Biotech S.L.	No results provided
DT-818	Small molecule (NCE)	<i>DMPK</i> toxic CUG-expanded mRNA	Phase I trial of DT-818 in healthy volunteers and adults with DM1	ISRCTN79964452	I	Est. completion 2027	44	Design Therapeutics	No results provided
Amlodipine	Small molecule (repurposed)	L-type voltage-gated calcium channels (Cav1.1)	Calcium channel blocker in DM1 (CAP DM1)	NCT07075965	I	Not yet recruiting	20	University of Rochester	No results provided
JUV-161	Recombinant fusion protein	<i>MAPK/ERK</i> and <i>PI3K/AKT</i> signaling pathways	First-in-human single ascending doses of JUV-161	NCT06918925	I	Recruiting	40	Juvena Therapeutics	No results provided
Lamotrigine ^a	Small molecule (repurposed)	Voltage-gated sodium channels (<i>Nav1.4</i>)	Lamotrigine as treatment of myotonia (mixed myotonic disorders)	NCT01939561	I	Completed (2015)	27	Rigshospitalet, Denmark	Demonstrated antimyotonic effect in mixed populations; no DM1-specific RCT data

Ab: antibody; NCE: new chemical entity; RCT: randomized controlled trial data.

^a Lamotrigine is included as a repurposed symptomatic agent. Although a Phase III trial in mixed myotonic disorders (NCT01939561) was completed in 2015, there is currently no active phase-defined clinical development program or ongoing randomized controlled trials specifically in DM1.

FIGURE 1

Therapeutic landscape and clinical/preclinical development pipeline for myotonic dystrophy type 1 (DM1). Overview of pharmacological strategies targeting the molecular and clinical manifestations of DM1, organized by mechanism of action and stage of development. The upper panel summarizes the pathogenic cascade, from expanded CTG repeats in DNA (DNAexp) to toxic CUG-expanded RNA hairpins, formation of RNA-MBNL (muscleblind-like) sequestration complexes and downstream protein dysregulation. Therapeutic approaches are positioned according to their primary molecular target or the specific disease manifestations addressed, including myotonia/pain and central nervous system (CNS) involvement. The central panel maps candidate therapies across development stages (preclinical, Phase I, Phase I/II, Phase II, Phase II/III and Phase III). Modalities are represented by shapes. Squares represent small molecules: repurposed (red) and new chemical entities (NCEs; green); circles represent nucleic-acid-based therapies: small interfering RNA (siRNA) targeting mRNA (brown), antisense oligonucleotides (ASO) targeting mRNA (blue) and ASO targeting miRNA (pink); triangles indicate genomic/transcriptomic engineering (gene therapy; yellow), hexagons denote biologics (turquoise) and ringed circles represent circular RNA platforms (purple). Developmental status is indicated as recruiting (R), active (A) or trial completed (/). An asterisk (*) denotes an open-label pilot study in adult DM1 patients not listed in publicly available trial databases. The vertical axis reflects increasing pharmaceutical advancement. The image was generated using [Biorender.com](https://www.biorender.com). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Tideglusib (AMO-02)

Tideglusib (also known as **AMO-02**) is an irreversible and non-ATP-competitive inhibitor of GSK3 β .^(p47) This repurposed small molecule can cross the blood–brain barrier and reach both the CNS and muscle tissue.^{(p18),(p48)} GSK3 β serves as a cellular hub regulating gene expression and neuronal function.^(p47) In DM1, elevated GSK3 β activity in muscle and brain leads to cyclin D3 loss, impairing CDK4-dependent CUGBP1 phosphorylation

and function.^{(p18),(p19),(p20)} By inhibiting GSK3 β , tideglusib restores normal phosphorylation and activity of CUGBP1, corrects the expression of genes misregulated in DM1 and reduces the levels of toxic mutant *DMPK* RNA and nuclear CUG foci.^{(p18),(p20)} In preclinical studies using DMSXL and HSA^{LR} mice, tideglusib treatment improved muscle strength, reduced myotonia and enhanced neuromotor activity during prenatal, postnatal and adult stages.^{(p18),(p20)} In human DM1 myoblasts,

tideglusib also decreased mutant RNA and corrected downstream molecular defects.^(p28) Additionally, recent clinical research in human patients has identified that active GSK3 β levels measured in peripheral blood mononuclear cells correlate with CTG repeat number and muscle weakness, serving as a potential biomarker.^(p49)

A Phase II clinical trial sponsored by AMO Pharma Ltd was conducted in adolescents and adults with congenital or juvenile-onset DM1 (NCT02858908; 2016-000067-16). The study demonstrated that tideglusib was safe and well tolerated, with preliminary evidence of modest improvements in muscle function, cognition and neuromuscular performance.^(p50) Following the completion of this initial trial, AMO Pharma initiated a Phase II/III study known as the REACH-CDM study (NCT03692312; 2016-004623-23). Although the trial did not meet its primary endpoint, it yielded clinically meaningful and statistically significant improvements in cognition, muscle biomarkers and motor function.

Over the past 3 years, participants who completed the REACH-CDM study were eligible for the REACH-CDMX open-label study (NCT05004129) to evaluate the long-term safety and efficacy of tideglusib for up to 52 weeks. This Phase II/III open-label study, now in the recruiting phase, also allows enrollment of individuals with either congenital or childhood-onset DM1 who are treatment-naïve.

Pitolisant

Pitolisant is a small-molecule inverse agonist of the histamine H₃ receptor, a presynaptic autoreceptor that inhibits histamine release in the brain. By blocking H₃ receptors, pitolisant enhances histamine release, stimulating postsynaptic H₁ and H₂ receptors and promoting wakefulness, vigilance and cognitive function.^(p51) It is approved for the treatment of excessive daytime sleepiness and cataplexy in narcolepsy and idiopathic hypersomnia^{(p52),(p53)} and is currently being evaluated in DM1. Excessive daytime sleepiness represents a major and highly prevalent clinical feature of DM1, significantly impacting quality of life.^(p54) While RNA toxicity in DM1 is known to affect multiple CNS pathways, the specific contribution of histaminergic dysfunction to sleepiness in this disorder remains unclear. More generally, alterations in neurotransmission, together with multi-system involvement, are thought to contribute to central fatigue and hypersomnolence in DM1.^{(p54),(p55)} In this context, pitolisant does not target the underlying molecular pathology, such as toxic CUG-expanded RNA or MBNL sequestration, but is hypothesized to act downstream by enhancing histaminergic neurotransmission and promoting wakefulness.

This small molecule was evaluated in a Phase II randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled signal-detection trial (NCT04886518) in adults with DM1 and excessive daytime sleepiness. A signal-detection trial is designed to identify early evidence of efficacy rather than provide definitive proof of benefit. Over an 11-week double-blind period, low- and high-dose pitolisant were compared with placebo. The trial demonstrated trends toward greater improvement in patient-reported daytime sleepiness and fatigue, with a safety profile consistent with pitolisant's use in narcolepsy. No new efficacy data have been reported in the past 2 years, as development has focused on formulation optimization, including a gastro-resistant formulation,

as recently reported by Harmony Biosciences.^(p56) These formulation efforts aim to support subsequent pivotal studies, including potential Phase III trials, before broader clinical evaluation in DM1.

Erythromycin (MYD-0124)

Erythromycin (MYD-0124) is a repurposed macrolide antibiotic that directly targets the molecular pathology of DM1 by binding expanded CUG repeat RNA, competitively preventing MBNL protein sequestration. By displacing MBNL from nuclear RNA foci, erythromycin restores normal splicing patterns in key transcripts, including *MBNL1*, *MBNL2*, *MAPT*, *CSNK1D* and *MPRIP*.^{(p57),(p58),(p59)} At the molecular level, it binds the CUG RNA hairpin via hydrogen bonds, π - π stacking, electrostatic interactions and van der Waals interactions with the U/U internal loops, dispersing RNA foci and correcting mis-splicing without reducing toxic RNA levels. *In vitro*, erythromycin rescued splicing of *MBNL1* exon 5, *MBNL2* exons 5 and 8, *MAPT* exon 2, *CSNK1D* exon 9 and *MPRIP* exon 9.^(p57) In DM1 patient-derived myotubes and HSA^{LR} mice, treatment led to significant rescue of splicing defects and partial improvement of myotonia, with minimal off-target effects and low cellular toxicity.^{(p58),(p60)}

Recent clinical evaluation in Japanese adult DM1 patients was performed in a multicenter Phase II trial (JRCT2051190069). The study reported a favorable safety profile, with only mild-to-moderate gastrointestinal side effects and no significant cardiac risks. Although improvements in splicing biomarkers, including *MBNL1* and *CACNA1S*, were observed, clinical outcomes were modest, reflecting the limited statistical power of the trial.^(p59) The authors concluded that a well-powered, multicenter Phase III study is needed to evaluate efficacy, building on these preliminary findings.

Amlodipine

Amlodipine, a dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker, is proposed for use in DM1 to mitigate the downstream effects of ion channel mis-splicing in cardiac and vascular tissues. In DM1, toxic RNA causes mis-splicing of key ion channel genes (*SCN5A*, *CACNA1C*, *CACNA1S*, *RYR2* and *KCNQ1*), destabilizing cardiac electrophysiology and predisposing individuals to arrhythmia and vascular dysfunction.^(p61) Mechanistically, amlodipine binds to the external, lipid-facing surface of L-type calcium channels, primarily CaV1.2 (encoded by *CACNA1C*), allosterically modulating channel conformation and reducing calcium influx in vascular smooth muscle and myocardium.^{(p62),(p63)} This action stabilizes excitability, lowers vascular resistance and afterload, provides symptomatic relief of hypertension and may reduce arrhythmia risk while partially compensating for abnormal calcium handling in DM1 hearts. Because it does not address the underlying genetic or splicing abnormalities, amlodipine remains a supportive, adjunctive therapy rather than a disease-modifying therapy.^{(p61),(p62)}

The translational potential of amlodipine in DM1 is planned to be evaluated in a Phase I clinical trial for safety and tolerability (NCT07075965). As of now, the trial status is 'not yet recruiting', and no clinical data are available.

DT-818

Developed by Design Therapeutics, **DT 818** is a small molecule originating from the GeneTAC platform, designed specifically to selectively target the mutant allele of the *DMPK* gene.^(p64)

GeneTAC compounds are heterobifunctional, with one moiety physically recognizing DNA sequences and the other interacting with the cellular transcriptional machinery, enabling precise modulation of gene expression without altering the underlying DNA.^(p65) DT 818 specifically binds the toxic expanded CTG repeats, reducing transcription of the mutant RNA and preventing the formation of toxic RNA structures, such as hairpins and nuclear foci.^(p64) In preclinical studies using patient-derived fibroblasts and myoblasts, DT 818 demonstrated potent, allele-selective knockdown of mutant *DMPK* RNA, reduced over 90% of toxic RNA foci, restored MBNL function and corrected splicing defects, with evidence of biodistribution to skeletal muscle and heart at well-tolerated doses in rodents.^(p66)

Design Therapeutics has obtained regulatory approval to develop DT 818 for DM1 outside the United States, with a Phase I multiple ascending dose (MAD) study planned in Australia (ISRCTN79964452), expected to begin in the first half of 2026.^(p67)

Lamotrigine

Lamotrigine is an antiepileptic voltage-gated sodium channel blocker that has been repurposed as a symptomatic antimyotonic agent. By reducing membrane hyperexcitability, it decreases myotonia through a mechanism analogous to mexiletine, although with a distinct pharmacological profile.^(p68) While robust randomized evidence supports its efficacy in nondystrophic myotonias, data in DM1 remain limited. A recent longitudinal open-label pilot study in adults with genetically confirmed DM1 reported improvements in hand function without serious adverse events (AEs), supporting a favorable short-term safety profile.^(p68) However, no placebo-controlled trials have been conducted specifically in DM1 to date. Although a randomized Phase III trial in mixed myotonic disorders, including DM1 (NCT01939561), was completed in 2015, this does not represent an active phase-defined development program for DM1, and current evidence in this population remains exploratory.

Biological therapies

Biological therapies are based on large macromolecules derived from living organisms or their components, aiming to improve the immune response. They include proteins, peptides, monoclonal antibodies or vaccines, offering high target specificity and the ability to modulate complex pathways.^(p69) Nevertheless, they also present limitations in terms of administration, short plasma half-life, frequent dosing, immunogenicity, complex pharmacokinetics, high production costs and strict storage requirements.^{(p70),(p71)}

JUV-161

In the context of biological therapies, the only drug currently under clinical evaluation is **JUV-161**, a recombinant fusion protein. Stem-cell-derived secreted factors are emerging as central mediators of regeneration and sources of rejuvenating therapies for aging- and disease-related dysfunction.^(p72) Building on this strategy, Juvena Therapeutics developed JUV-161, a biological therapy designed to agonistically target the *MAPK/ERK* and *PI3K/AKT* signaling pathways.^(p73) Persistent activation of the *MAPK/ERK* pathway has been reported in DM1, which is associated with defects in muscle cell differentiation.^{(p74),(p75)} Impaired

AKT signaling has also been reported in DM1 skeletal muscle, contributing to defective anabolic responses and muscle wasting.^(p26) By restoring *ERK* and *AKT* signaling toward physiological levels, JUV-161 enhances myogenic differentiation, supports myocyte survival, improves protein synthesis and ameliorates metabolic defects, thereby counteracting muscle weakness and atrophy in DM1.^(p73) To assess its preclinical efficacy, JUV-161 was evaluated in a pan-inducible TREDT960I transgenic mouse model expressing expanded CUG repeats from the *DMPK* gene, which recapitulates key features of DM1 muscle pathology. Treatment with JUV-161 significantly improved grip strength, increased tibialis anterior muscle cross-sectional area and promoted a shift toward fast-twitch type-2X/B fibers in the soleus.^(p73) High receptor sequence homology across species, together with supportive pharmacokinetic, pharmacodynamic and safety studies in rat and dog models, underscores the translational potential of these findings.^(p73)

Over the past 3 years, JUV-161 advanced from the preclinical to the clinical stage. The safety, tolerability and pharmacokinetics of single subcutaneous doses of JUV-161 are currently being evaluated in a Phase I randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial (NCT06918925) involving healthy volunteers. The study includes up to five cohorts, with a starting dose of 0.10 mg/kg, determined based on preclinical data. JUV-161 treatment may enhance muscle strength, endurance and mass, as well as improve glucose regulation, potentially reducing muscle atrophy in adult-onset DM1 patients. This could also result in faster walking speeds and a lower incidence of falls.

Nucleic-acid-based therapies

NATs use DNA, RNA or synthetic oligonucleotides as therapeutic agents. Despite their structural diversity, NATs share a unifying principle: therapeutic nucleic acid sequences hybridize to endogenous targets through Watson–Crick base pairing. This interaction enables precise regulation of gene expression by silencing transcripts, replacing defective sequences or editing genomic loci, ultimately achieving long-lasting effects across a wide range of diseases.^(p76) However, a major challenge for NATs is efficient delivery. Nucleic acids are large, negatively charged macromolecules, and the negative polarization of cellular membranes restricts the entry of NATs due to their similar charge. In addition, they are biologically unstable and prone to degradation by endogenous nucleases, while the small fraction of unmodified NATs that manage to enter cells often becomes trapped in endosomes and is subsequently degraded in lysosomes.^{(p76),(p77)} To overcome these limitations, NATs are typically chemically modified and conjugated with other molecules to enhance their stability, facilitate cellular uptake and promote endosomal escape.^(p77)

AOC 1001 (*del-desiran*)

AOC 1001, developed by Avidity Biosciences and abbreviated as *del-desiran* from its full name, delpacibart etedesiran, is the only NAT currently in Phase III clinical trial for the treatment of DM1. AOC 1001 is a therapy based on small interfering RNA (siRNA), short RNA molecules of 21–23 nucleotides that hybridize to targeted sense-strand RNAs through base complementarity, leading to the degradation or inhibition of the corresponding target transcripts.^(p78) AOC 1001 targets a nonrepetitive sequence

of *DMPK* mRNA, thereby reducing overall *DMPK* transcript levels and indirectly alleviating RNA toxicity. This reduction decreases the sequestration of MBNL proteins by toxic CUG-expanded RNA, which contributes to the correction of splicing defects and amelioration of downstream disease manifestations.^(p79) To enhance targeted delivery to skeletal, cardiac and smooth muscle, AOC 1001 is conjugated to a monoclonal antibody against **transferrin receptor 1 (TfR1)**, a receptor highly expressed in muscle tissues.^{(p79),(p80)}

AOC 1001 illustrates the intensification of pharmaceutical efforts over the past 3 years to develop therapies for DM1, as reflected by Novartis' very recent announcement of its acquisition of Avidity Biosciences, with the transaction of the precision cardiology assets expected to close by mid-2026 (see [Box 1](#) for details). The safety and tolerability of *del-desiran* were first

Box 1 Strategic inflection points in DM1 therapeutics (2022–2026).

I. Clinical milestones and pipeline evolution

The shift toward enhanced delivery and transcriptomic correction.

- Mar 2026 | Sarepta Therapeutics: First clinical data reported for SRP-1003 (siRNA, avb6 integrin-targeted delivery platform) in a Phase I/II trial. Early results show dose-dependent muscle exposure, initial biomarker activity and favorable tolerability without dose-limiting toxicity. Preliminary data also indicate target engagement with *DMPK* knockdown following a single dose, although this is based on a limited number of patients and is pending full dataset disclosure. Sarepta Therapeutics News.
- Mar 2026 | Arthex Biotech: ATX-01, ARTHEx's investigational RNA therapeutic designed to inhibit miR-23b, a natural suppressor of MBNL, was granted Fast Track Designation by the FDA for the treatment of DM1. Arthex News.
- Mar 2026 | PepGen Inc.: A partial clinical hold has been placed by the FDA on the Phase II FREEDOM2-DM1 multiple ascending dose trial of PGN-EDODM1, despite previously reported robust splicing correction in earlier-phase studies. This highlights emerging regulatory and safety considerations for high-dose oligonucleotide delivery approaches. PepGen News.
- Feb 2026 | Vertex Pharmaceuticals: Dosing continues in the GALILEO Phase I/II trial for VX-670. This candidate utilizes a cyclic peptide-linked oligonucleotide to bypass delivery barriers into muscle and CNS. Full enrollment is projected for mid-2026. Vertex News.
- Jan 2026 | Juvena Therapeutics: Announced a \$33.5M Series B (led by Bison Ventures and Eli Lilly) to advance JUV-161. Unlike RNA-targeting agents, this AI-engineered regenerative biologic focuses on restoring myogenesis and muscle metabolism. Preclinical data showed significant strength improvement. Juvena Therapeutics.
- Dec 2025 | Arrakis Therapeutics: Unveiled preclinical proof-of-concept for its oral rSM. The lead candidate binds

to CUG repeats, effectively releasing sequestered MBNL1 proteins and reversing myotonia. An Investigational new drug (IND) filing is slated for 2026, marking a shift toward oral, systemic DM1 therapies. Arrakis Therapeutics.

- Nov 2025 | Dyne Therapeutics: Reported that the ACHIEVE trial for z-basivarsen (DYNE-101)—an antibody-oligonucleotide conjugate—will complete enrollment in early Q2 2026. Dyne targets a Biologics License Application (BLA) submission for Accelerated Approval in Q3 2027, with a potential Q1 2028 market entry. Dyne Therapeutics.
- Nov 2025 | Design Therapeutics: Nominated DT-818, a small molecule GeneTAC™ (Gene Targeted Chimera), for clinical development. Phase I MAD trials are scheduled for 1H 2026 in Australia, targeting the reduction of toxic RNA foci. Design Therapeutics.
- Sept 2025 | PepGen Inc.: Achieved a major clinical breakthrough with PGN-EDODM1, reporting a 53.7% mean splicing correction at a 15 mg/kg dose in the FREEDOM-DM1 Phase I study. The candidate utilizes EDO technology to optimize intracellular concentration. PepGen News.
- July 2025 | Sarepta and Arrowhead: Confirmed a \$100M milestone payment for SRP-1003 (formerly ARO-DM1), an investigational siRNA. The Phase I/II study is currently escalating doses to assess the durability of RNA interference in DM1 patients. Sarepta Therapeutics.

II. M&A and ecosystem consolidation

Validating the DM1 market through high-stakes capital allocation.

- Oct 2025 | Novartis acquires Avidity Biosciences (\$12B): In the largest DM1-related deal to date, Novartis integrated Avidity's AOC™ platform. The acquisition centers on *del-desiran* (AOC 1001), currently the most advanced candidate in late-stage development for DM1. Novartis Official.
- Nov 2024 | Arrowhead and Sarepta Global License: A deal valued at up to \$10 billion in potential milestones, focused on RNAi-based precision medicines, signaling massive confidence in siRNA for neuromuscular indications. Arrowhead Pharma.
- Dec 2022 | Vertex and Entrada Collaboration: A \$250M upfront partnership to leverage Entrada's Endosomal Escape Vehicle (EEV™) platform, specifically for the ENTR-701 program, aiming to solve the 'endosomal trapping' bottleneck in DM1 therapy. Entrada Tx.

III. Executive summary: The 'third wave' of DM1 therapy

The DM1 landscape has transitioned from basic ASOs to a 'third wave' of precision delivery. This period is characterized by the following developments:

1. Conjugation science: The dominance of antibody-oligonucleotide conjugates (Dyne and Avidity/Novartis) and EEVs (Entrada/Vertex) in reaching deep muscle tissue.
2. Oral modalities: The emergence of small molecules (Arrakis and Design) that could disrupt the injectable-dominated market.
3. Regenerative biologics: A shift from just 'fixing RNA' to 'restoring muscle function' (Juvena).

demonstrated in the MARINA trial (NCT05027269; 2021–2023), a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled Phase I/II study evaluating single and multiple ascending intravenous doses in 38 adults with DM1. MARINA assessed key molecular biomarkers, including spliceopathy correction and *DMPK* mRNA knock-down, and explored clinical activity through measures of myotonia, muscle strength and mobility. In MARINA, *del-desiran* produced robust, dose-dependent reductions in *DMPK* mRNA in skeletal muscle, accompanied by broad, concentration-dependent correction of mis-splicing and clinically meaningful improvements in myotonia, muscle strength and mobility compared with placebo, with an acceptable safety and tolerability profile consistent with previous reports.^(p81) Participants completing MARINA were eligible for the MARINA-OLE extension study (also completed; 2022–2025), an open-label Phase II trial assessing long-term safety and clinical progression, with placebo-treated individuals transitioning to active treatment. *Del-desiran* is now being investigated in the pivotal Phase III HARBOR trial (NCT06411288), a multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study enrolling 150 participants aged 16–65 years. HARBOR aims to determine the efficacy of *del-desiran* on myotonia, muscle strength and daily function while continuing to monitor safety. Participants will be randomized in a 1:1 ratio to receive either *del-desiran* or placebo, delivered as intravenous infusions at intervals of approximately 8 weeks for a total of seven doses, for approximately 12.5 months. The HARBOR study also includes an open-label extension study, HARBOR-OLE (NCT07008469), which allows enrollment only of participants who have completed the parent HARBOR trial. The study includes a screening period of up to 4–8 weeks depending on the prior parent trial, followed by a treatment period of up to 4 years, with intravenous dosing every 8 weeks.

DYNE-101

DYNE-101 (zeleciment basivarsen) is a muscle-targeted antisense oligonucleotide (ASO) designed to directly address the genetic cause of DM1. It consists of a gapmer-type ASO conjugated to a TfR1-binding fragment antigen-binding (Fab) antibody via the FORCE™ platform, which facilitates efficient uptake into skeletal and cardiac muscle and nuclear delivery of the oligonucleotide.^{(p82),(p83)} Once internalized, the ASO binds mutant *DMPK* transcripts and recruits RNase H, leading to selective degradation of toxic nuclear RNA, reduction of RNA foci and partial restoration of normal splicing. This mechanism corrects spliceopathy across multiple DM1-relevant transcripts, including canonical biomarkers such as *CLCN1*, *INSR* and *TNNT2*, which are associated with myotonia, insulin resistance and cardiac conduction abnormalities.^{(p83),(p84),(p85)} Preclinical studies in HSA^{LR} and TfR1^{hu/mu}; DMSXL mouse models, as well as patient-derived myoblasts, demonstrated dose-dependent reduction of mutant *DMPK* RNA, durable correction of alternative splicing and improvement of myotonia and muscle function, with superior efficacy compared to unconjugated ASOs.^(p83)

Over the past 3 years, DYNE-101 has advanced into clinical development and is currently being evaluated in the randomized, placebo-controlled Phase I/II ACHIEVE trial (NCT05481879; 2022-000889-18) conducted in adults with DM1. The IV regimen is converging on 6.8 mg/kg every 8 weeks as a putative registrational dose. Interim data indicate robust,

dose-dependent muscle delivery, consistent correction of alternative splicing across a multigene panel and functional improvements in myotonia (hand-opening time), muscle strength, timed functional tests and patient-reported outcomes such as DM1-ACTIVc and MDHI, alongside a generally favorable safety profile.^{(p86),(p87)} Additionally, DYNE-101 has received Orphan Drug designation in the United States and the EU, Fast Track designation from the FDA and Breakthrough Therapy designation, underscoring its potential as a first-in-class disease-modifying therapy for DM1.^(p88)

VX-670

VX-670 (formerly ENTR-701) is a peptide-conjugated phosphorodiamidate morpholino oligonucleotide (PMO) antisense therapy under development by Vertex Pharmaceuticals for DM1. It is designed as a steric-blocking ASO that binds directly to the expanded CUG repeat tract within mutant *DMPK* mRNA. By preventing the sequestration of MBNL proteins, VX-670 aims to reduce nuclear RNA foci and restore alternative splicing across transcripts dysregulated in DM1.^(p89)

VX-670 was originally developed by Entrada Therapeutics under the name ENTR-701 and was in-licensed by Vertex Pharmaceuticals, with the transfer of rights completed in February 2023^(p90) (see more details in **Box 1**). It has since advanced into clinical evaluation, and it is currently being investigated in the ongoing Phase I/II randomized, placebo-controlled GALILEO study (NCT06185764), followed by a long-term open-label extension study (NCT06926621). These studies aim to assess safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, including correction of alternative splicing in muscle, and exploratory functional outcomes in adults with DM1.

PGN-EDODM1

PGN-EDODM1 is an enhanced delivery oligonucleotide (EDO) developed by PepGen, consisting of a phosphorodiamidate morpholino oligonucleotide conjugated to a proprietary cell-penetrating peptide. The PMO component is designed to bind the expanded CUG repeat tract in mutant *DMPK* mRNA, thereby preventing MBNL sequestration, reducing nuclear RNA foci and correcting downstream alternative splicing abnormalities while preserving normal *DMPK* transcript expression.^(p91) Preclinical studies in the HSA^{LR} mouse model and additional DM1 models have demonstrated dose-dependent muscle accumulation, reduction of RNA foci, correction of mis-splicing in disease-relevant transcripts and improvement in myotonia and muscle function.^(p92)

PGN-EDODM1 has progressed to clinical evaluation and is being studied in the Phase I single-ascending-dose FREEDOM-DM1 trial (NCT06204809), the Phase II multiple-ascending-dose FREEDOM2-DM1 study (NCT06667453) and an ongoing open-label extension (NCT07220603). In 2024, PGN-EDODM1 received the Orphan Drug designation from the FDA.^(p93) Interim results have demonstrated dose-dependent splicing correction in skeletal muscle, accompanied by corresponding increases in tissue drug concentration.^(p94) However, the FDA has placed a partial clinical hold on the Phase II FREEDOM2-DM1 trial due to questions regarding previously submitted preclinical pharmacology and toxicology data. PepGen is actively addressing these queries through the submission of additional analyses, including unblinded clinical data. Outside the United States, the trial is

ongoing, with regulatory clearance obtained in multiple regions and dose escalation to 10 mg/kg proceeding following the Data Safety Monitoring Board's recommendation.^(p95)

ARO-DM1 (SRP-1003)

ARO-DM1 employs RNAi to selectively suppress the expression of the *DMPK* gene. Its delivery strategy relies on encapsulating the nucleic acid therapeutic in muscle-targeted nanoparticles, thereby reducing the accumulation of toxic *DMPK* transcripts containing expanded CTG repeats nonallele manner. This reduction alleviates spliceopathy in affected muscle cells and mitigates disease symptoms.^{(p96),(p97)}

In the past 3 years, the rights to ARO-DM1, originally developed by Arrowhead Pharmaceuticals, were recently acquired by Sarepta Therapeutics at the beginning of 2025^(p98) (see **Box 1** for details). ARO-DM1, now called SRP-1003, is the second candidate developed by Arrowhead Pharmaceuticals to use the Targeted RNAi Molecule (TRiM™) platform, which enables ligand-mediated delivery of RNAi therapeutics to skeletal muscle and is designed to support multitissue targeting while maintaining a simple structure.^(p99) Regarding clinical evaluation, a Phase I/II double-blind, placebo-controlled, dose-escalation trial is currently recruiting adults aged 18–65 with DM1 to assess the safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of single and MADs of the drug compared with placebo (NCT06138743). Recently, early results from this Phase I/II study demonstrated dose-dependent muscle exposure, early biomarker modulation and a favorable tolerability profile. Additionally, Sarepta Therapeutics has generated proof-of-concept data showing that a single dose of SRP-1003 achieves *DMPK* mRNA knockdown, with mostly mild-to-moderate AEs that were not dose-dependent.^(p100)

SAR446268

Although the NATs described earlier show promising efficacy for the treatment of DM1, they will require repeated dosing to maintain therapeutic levels. However, the combination of NATs delivered as a gene therapy using adeno-associated virus (AAV) offers the potential for a single-administration treatment, as the AAV vector persists within the nucleus as an episome, enabling long-term expression of the therapeutic agent in target cells.^(p101)

SAR446268, developed by Sanofi, is an AAV-delivered RNAi therapy that silences *DMPK* expression and enhances muscle-targeted delivery. The system comprises an AAV capsid optimized for high muscle transduction, a muscle-specific promoter and an artificial miRNA carrying a *DMPK*-targeting guide sequence within the miR-155 scaffold.^(p101) In preclinical evaluations using both cellular and animal models of DM1, AAV-mediated delivery of artificial miRNAs resulted in a significant reduction in *DMPK* RNA levels, along with improvements in molecular, pathological and clinically relevant disease markers.^(p102) Preclinical studies in nonhuman primates demonstrated the safety and efficacy of SAR446268, showing good tolerability and effective downregulation of *DMPK* expression.^{(p102),(p103)} This promising safety data enabled the progression of SAR446268 into a Phase I/II open-label, single-arm study to evaluate its safety, tolerability and efficacy in participants aged 10–50 years with noncongenital DM1 (NCT06844214). In 2024, SAR446268 was granted orphan drug designations by the FDA and EMA, and in 2025, it was awarded Fast Track designation by the FDA to accelerate the development and review of drugs

intended to treat serious conditions and address unmet medical needs.^(p103) However, AAV-based therapies also present several limitations, including the need to monitor long-term expression and immune responses against the vector or therapeutic miRNA, limited CNS penetration for addressing neurological symptoms, and patient heterogeneity in CUG repeat length and somatic mosaicism, which may affect therapeutic efficacy and necessitate biomarker-guided dosing strategies.^(p101)

ATX-01

ATX 01, a fatty-acid-conjugated ASO developed by Arthex Biotech, employs a unique therapeutic strategy compared to other NATs. While most NATs target the underlying disease-causing gene, *DMPK*, to reduce toxic RNA transcripts that sequester MBNL proteins, ATX 01 alleviates MBNL depletion by specifically inhibiting the activity of miR 23b, a natural MBNL repressor, with a perfectly complementary oligonucleotide (antimiR). Antagonists of miR 23b have been shown to recuperate MBNL protein levels in human DM1 myoblasts as well as in HSA^{LR} mice.^{(p25),(p104)} Notably, antimiR 23b treatment not only increased MBNL protein levels but also reduced RNA toxicity by lowering *DMPK* transcripts and ribonuclear foci, ultimately correcting key cellular defects such as spliceopathy.^(p105) To enhance the delivery and efficacy of antimiR molecules, Arthex Biotech developed the EntrRy™ platform, which combines the specificity of antimiRs with a hydrophobic moiety to enable highly selective targeting of specific tissues.^(p106) The current version of ATX 01 is conjugated to oleic acid, facilitating preferential delivery to muscle and brain tissue in preclinical models.^(p107) Moreover, ATX 01 demonstrated positive preclinical data in the brain of the DMSXL mouse model, rescuing functional and molecular cognitive dysfunction.^(p108)

ATX 01 was granted orphan drug designation by both the FDA and EMA in 2022.^(p109) In 2024, it received rare pediatric disease designation from the FDA,^(p110) and more recently, in March 2026, it was granted Fast Track designation by the FDA.^(p111) The first patient was subsequently dosed in the global, multicenter Phase I–IIa Arthemir trial (NCT06300307), a double-blind, placebo-controlled study evaluating single- and multiple-ascending doses in participants with classic DM1 to assess safety and tolerability. Additionally, the trial aims to evaluate target engagement in muscle using biomarkers, including MBNL1 protein levels and RNA splicing index.^(p107)

Preclinical developments

Among the various 'small molecules' currently undergoing preclinical evaluation (**Table 2**), RNA-targeted small molecules (**rSMs**) have emerged as a promising therapeutic candidate. Developed by Arrakis Therapeutics, rSMs are rationally designed to specifically recognize and bind RNA hairpin structures formed by pathogenic expanded CUG repeats. Through this interaction, rSMs disrupt nuclear RNA foci and prevent the sequestration of the MBNL1 protein, thereby rescuing normal splicing levels.^(p112) Preclinical studies show that in DM1 patient-derived myocytes, Arrakis' rSMs neutralize repeat RNA aggregates and correct splicing defects, while in HSA^{LR} mice, they reverse myotonia and improve mis-splicing.^(p113) In addition, rSMs are administered orally, which represents a significant advantage for clinical

TABLE 2

Preclinical programs for DM1.

Preclinical program	Type	Biological target	Sponsor	Preclinical model
RNA-targeted small molecules	Small molecules	DMPK mRNA (CUG repeats)	Arrakis Therapeutics	Patient-derived myocytes, HSA ^{LR} mice
LoQus23 MMR inhibitors	Small molecules	MMR (specifically MSH3)	LoQus23 Therapeutics	Preclinical studies were only conducted in Huntington's disease models
EF-210 (CUG-PPR1)	AAV-PPR protein	Toxic CUG-repeat RNA	EditForce Inc.	Patient-derived myoblasts, CUG-expansion-expressing cell systems and HSA ^{LR} mice
RGT-DM1	Small molecule	MMR (specifically PMS1)	Rgenta Therapeutics	Not specified
MDL-202	AAV-CRISPR base editing	DMPK Genomic DNA	Modalis Therapeutics	Not specified
NoctuRNA circRNA	Circular RNA therapeutic	Toxic CUG-repeat RNA/ RNA secondary structures	NoctuRNA Therapeutics	Not specified
KNA-129	ASO	Toxic CUG-repeat RNA	Kinea Bio	Not specified

translation.^(p112) As another preclinical strategy, LoQus23 Therapeutics is developing small molecules that target DNA mismatch repair (MMR) proteins, which normally maintain microsatellite stability but can paradoxically drive the expansion of triplet repeats.^{(p114),(p115)} Their strategy focuses on inhibiting key MMR factors, primarily MSH3, a component of the MutS β complex, using an allosteric small molecule against MSH3.^(p116) By downregulating MMR proteins, the small molecules developed by LoQus23 have the potential to limit or prevent pathogenic repeat expansion in affected tissues. Preclinical studies to date have been conducted in Huntington's disease models, yet the approach may be applicable to other triplet repeat disorders, including DM1.^(p117) Following a similar strategy to LoQus23, Rgenta Therapeutics is developing **RGT-DM1**, a small molecule that inhibits the expression of the MMR protein PMS1.^(p118) PMS1 is a genetically validated target for halting somatic repeat expansion in repeat expansion disorders.^(p114) By inducing targeted mis-splicing and subsequent degradation of *PMS1* mRNA, the drug effectively reduces the levels of the PMS1 protein, thereby stabilizing the genome and halting disease progression by preventing the further accumulation of toxic *DMPK* RNA over time.^(p118) In addition to MMR factor inhibition, enhancing the activity of FAN1, a nuclease that counteracts the effects of MMR proteins, has also emerged as a potential therapeutic target to prevent repeat expansions.^{(p119),(p120)}

In the context of 'biological therapies', EditForce leads to the development of preclinical treatments for DM1. The EditForce platform is based on pentatricopeptide repeat (PPR) proteins, originally discovered in plants, which can be engineered to bind RNA with high sequence specificity. These proteins may be fused to different effector domains to perform specific functions, and the complete genetic construct can be packaged into an AAV.^(p121) Their preclinical-stage drug, **EF 210**, is an AAV based therapy that delivers the engineered RNA binding protein CUG PPR1, which lacks an effector domain, to muscle tissue. CUG PPR1 specifically recognizes expanded CUG repeat tracts in the toxic *DMPK* transcripts, binding to them with high sequence selectivity and thereby preventing MBNL1 sequestration and downstream splicing defects.^(p122) Proof-of-concept studies demonstrated that CUG-PPR1 mitigates RNA toxicity

induced by CUG expansions in DM1 cell models, including patient-derived myoblasts and CUG-expansion-expressing cell systems, preventing the sequestration of MBNL proteins. This action restores functional MBNL protein levels, reduces RNA foci and normalizes splicing activity and muscle function.^(p123) A single systemic administration of the AAV9 vector delivering CUG-PPR1 resulted in long-term therapeutic effects, including improvement of myotonia and restoration of splicing activity in the HSA^{LR} mouse model of DM1.^{(p122),(p123)} Additionally, non-GLP toxicology and biodistribution studies in both mice and nonhuman primates have also been completed.^(p122)

Within the 'gene therapy' field, Modalis Therapeutics is developing **MDL-202** for the treatment of DM1, using the CRISPR-GNDM epigenome editing technology, aiming to inhibit the transcription of *DMPK* mRNA and, therefore, allowing MBNL protein to perform its regular function.^(p124) The system combines dCas9, an epigenome editor/modulator, and a guide RNA, all packaged in a single AAV vector for efficient delivery. In target cells, CRISPR-GNDM is expressed as the GNDM protein, which binds to the promoter of the target gene to modulate transcription, repressing *DMPK* transcript expression.^(p125) MDL-202 remains at the preclinical optimization level, with no preclinical data officially published to date.

Innovative nucleic-acid-based therapies are being pursued by companies such as NoctuRNA Therapeutics, which is developing **circular RNAs (circRNAs)** as a therapeutic approach to target aberrant RNA secondary structures implicated in various diseases. In the context of DM1, these circRNAs are designed to recognize and hybridize to regions proximal to pathological RNA conformations, thereby interfering with their stability and preventing the sequestration of MBNL proteins.^(p126) Their candidate for the treatment of DM1 has been evaluated in *in vitro* models, while *in vivo* studies have been conducted to assess pharmacokinetics. Pharmacodynamic assessments in *in vivo* models are ongoing; however, detailed information regarding the experimental design, models used or efficacy outcomes has not been disclosed.^(p127) Another emerging preclinical approach is represented by **KNA 129**, developed by Kinea Bio. KNA 129 is described by the company as a systemically delivered oligonucleotide therapy designed to target toxic CUG repeats, with the

aim of reducing RNA foci, releasing sequestered MBNL proteins and correcting downstream spliceopathy in skeletal and cardiac muscle, and potentially in the CNS, similar to other CUG-directed ASO platforms in development.^(p128) KNA 129 utilizes the BioDrone nanovesicle platform, which enables repeated delivery of genetic cargo without eliciting significant immune responses.^(p129) Detailed preclinical data have not yet been disclosed.

Lastly, a different therapy strategy for DM1, based on a ‘decoy’ approach, has been developed at the Institute of Myology (Paris, France). This approach relies on a modified MBNL1 protein (MBNL1Δ), engineered to competitively bind pathogenic CUG-expanded RNA transcripts and displace endogenous MBNL1. In DM1 cellular and mouse models, AAV9-mediated delivery of MBNL1Δ corrected aberrant alternative splicing, improved muscle phenotype and reduced myotonia, with sustained effects following a single administration.^(p130)

Nonpharmacological therapeutic interventions in DM1

Nonpharmacological interventions have previously been considered an important adjunct to pharmacological and molecular approaches. In other neuromuscular diseases, including Duchenne muscular dystrophy and facioscapulohumeral muscular dystrophy, structured exercise and rehabilitation programs have demonstrated benefits in functional capacity, fatigue and quality of life.^{(p131),(p132)} These results provide a conceptual framework for similar strategies in DM1, given the multisystemic nature of the pathology.

Lastly, most of the nonpharmacological research activity in DM1 has focused on exercise-based and rehabilitation interventions, as reflected by both recent publications and registered clinical trials. Interventional studies published during this period indicate that aerobic and resistance exercise are feasible and generally safe for individuals with DM1 and may lead to improvements in muscle strength, aerobic capacity and patient-reported outcomes.^{(p133),(p134)} These findings are supported by mechanistic studies showing that exercise can partially counteract mitochondrial dysfunction, reduced oxidative capacity and muscle structural abnormalities characteristic of DM1.^(p135) Importantly, recent mechanistic evidence has further strengthened this rationale. A 12-week structured strength-training intervention in women with DM1 demonstrated improvements in mitochondrial content, ADP-stimulated respiration, oxidative-stress regulation and muscle-fiber ultrastructure, with high adherence and no major AEs reported.^(p136) Together with previous aerobic-training studies, these data support the biological plausibility of exercise as a disease-modifying supportive intervention, although sample sizes remain limited and long-term outcomes are largely unexplored.^{(p133),(p134)} Additionally, multiple exercise- and rehabilitation-focused clinical trials registered in the past 3 years reflect an increasingly diversified landscape. These include sex-specific strength-training protocols (NCT05400629 and NCT04018820), acute resistance-exercise studies (NCT05036447), remote or tele-rehabilitation programs (NCT05560438) and personalized training interventions for rare neuromuscular disorders that include DM1 (NCT05081791).

Despite the growing number of completed studies, public availability of results remains limited, significantly constraining cross-study comparison and evidence synthesis.

In parallel, an emerging subset of trials has investigated technology-assisted rehabilitation and assistive or robotic devices. Studies such as technology-assisted upper-limb rehabilitation with remote assessments (NCT05560438) and the evaluation of lower-limb assistive or robotic devices (NCT05199246) primarily address feasibility, safety and usability and should be interpreted as technology-evaluation studies rather than definitive efficacy trials. In contrast to exercise-based interventions, nutritional strategies remain poorly investigated in DM1. No structured nutritional clinical trials specifically targeting DM1 have been registered or reported in recent years, except for limited exploratory work on nutritional supplementation discussed in previous reviews (e.g. heat-shock protein co-inducers or metabolic modulators).^{(p44),(p137)}

Conclusions and future challenges

The therapeutic landscape of DM1 has entered a phase of unprecedented translational maturity, with multiple therapeutic modalities advancing toward clinical application and the realistic prospect of disease-modifying interventions on the horizon. Despite this remarkable progress, fundamental challenges remain unsolved, including profound clinical and molecular heterogeneity, an urgent need for sensitive and predictive biomarkers, and the development of delivery strategies capable of effectively targeting multisystem involvement, particularly the central nervous system.

The inherent instability of repeat expansions and the growing number of downstream dysregulated mechanisms present major challenges in DM1. One notable example is the recent recognition of significant gut microbiota alterations in the gastrointestinal tract of DM1 patients,^(p138) also observed in the DMSXL mouse model for the disease.^(p139) Unexpected clinical manifestations have also been identified. For instance, autism spectrum disorder rates are markedly higher than in the general population, as well as progeroid features found in DM1, with success demonstrated in proof-of-concept *in vitro* and *in vivo* therapeutic intervention.^(p140) These observations underscore that therapeutic success will require both biological precision and long-term monitoring. Thus, the increasing recognition of DM1 as a complex, multisystem and aging-related disorder underscores the importance of moving beyond muscle-centric endpoints toward integrated approaches that address systemic decline, neuropsychiatric manifestations and quality of life. Future advances will likely depend on combining molecular therapies with improved clinical assessment tools, digital monitoring and multidisciplinary care frameworks capable of capturing subtle but meaningful changes across disease domains.

Ultimately, the success of emerging therapies will depend on a shift toward personalized precision medicine, in which treatment strategies are tailored to each patient’s molecular and clinical profile. In this evolving paradigm, placing the patient, not only the mutation, at the center of therapeutic decision-making will be essential for achieving meaningful and durable clinical benefits.

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Yasmine Ferchichi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Investigation. **Àngela Natividad:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Investigation. **Rubén Artero:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Arturo López-Castel:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of interests

R.A. is a co-founder and scientific advisor at Arthex Biotech and holds a minor equity interest in the company. R.A. is also a co-inventor on patents PCT/EP2017/073685 and EP22382493, which are currently licensed to Arthex Biotech.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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